

Measuring The Industry Literacy Of Businesses In The Ovine Sector: A Research In The Center And Districts of Kastamonu

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Abstract

This study aims to show that Kastamonu central district has the right to draw individual, commercial and agricultural loans, credit industry literacy levels of credit customers in the ovine sector, and which age/gender and so on are the most likely industry literate groups. The research found that the level of industry literacy was high, with data collected using 140 businesses in the small livestock sector and face-to-face polling techniques. In light of their responses to questions raised in the survey to gauge industry levels, the survey attempts to identify problems that appear to be related. Based on the results of the research, families in commercial enterprises operating in the Minor livestock sector have a high level of industry literacy. In addition, women are found to have a higher appetite for risk than men. Suggestions have been developed about what to do to improve the industry literacy of loan customers in Kastamonu. .

Keywords: Industry Literacy, Ovine Sector, Kastamonu

1.Introduction

Financial literacy has emerged as a very popular concept in the last 20 years. The banking industry is working to get people to make good financial decisions, to get the skills they need. Financial literacy means the knowledge and skills to make financial decisions. It's very clear that without having to separate the countryside, half of the adult population in the world doesn't understand financial concepts enough. In fact, a study by the OECD found that half of the population of European Union member states do not know about important definitions. Low-income groups and disadvantaged groups are also considered acute ignorance. The two main causes of this global phenomenon are the difficulty and lack of interest in accessing information (URL-1). In access to financial literacy, communities sometimes display a willingness to access information. These times, it can often be listed as "world-related war", "crisis", "covid-like epidemics, and important events." The majority of consumers are younger than most of the financial risks and financial opportunities as a result of the significant events described above. They tend to act on traditional knowledge of how debt is managed. In fact, while everyone has some information, they don't really know what information they really have. Most people don't know the concept of compound interest or money's time value. But when asked how inflation has changed the monetary dimensions over time, and what the interest rates banks charge are, the majority pretty much agrees.

In today's world, it's important to prepare for emergencies, to compete in time, to make it easier for an individual to achieve its goals, to teach future generations of information after itself, to see why seemingly unattainable goals are at least possible, to show that achieving seemingly impenetrable goals is within reach, to build one's confidence in oneself, to respond less about unpredictable outcomes, and to minimize impact about nonpredictable results.

The foundations of financial literacy require a simple skill at heart, but individuals who have difficulty managing households are afraid of taking risks

Anatolia has been home to many civilizations for many years. Each living civilization used and developed different farming practices, driven by the breadth of geography and the various climate characteristics that can be seen. Ovine sector has a considerable share in the practice of wayer cultivation. Ovine breeding is an important sector among agricultural activities in our country, which is highly agricultural given its natural resources and plant diversity.

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In the world and in our country, ovine animals are not just good for the consumption of red meat, but they're good for a lot of things, like leather, milk. The number of animals in our country is indicated in the Table 1 below.²

Table 1: Ovine in Turkey

Year	Sheep	Goat	Total
2002	25.173.706	6.780.094	31.953.800
2003	25.431.539	6.771.675	32.203.214
2004	25.201.155	6.609.937	31.811.092
2005	25.304.325	6.517.464	31.821.789
2006	25.616.912	6.643.294	32.260.206
2007	25.475.293	6.286.358	31.761.651
2008	23.974.591	5.593.561	29.568.152
2009	21.749.508	5.128.285	26.877.793
2010	23.089.691	6.293.233	29.382.924
2011	25.031.565	7.277.953	32.309.518
2012	27.425.233	8.357.286	35.782.519
2013	29.284.247	9.225.548	38.509.795
2014	31.140.244	10.344.936	41.485.180
2015	31.507.934	10.416.166	41.924.100
2016	30.983.933	10.345.299	41.329.232
2017	33.677.636	10.634.672	44.312.308
2018	35.194.972	10.922.427	46.117.399
2019	37.276.050	11.205.429	48.481.479
2020	42.126.781	11.985.845	54.112.626
2021	45.177.690	12.341.514	57.519.204
2022	46.122.627	12.324.928	58.447.555

Source: TUIK, Retrieved 23.10.2022

In our country, the province of Kastamonu, in the Western Black Sea Region of the Black Sea, has a surface area of 13,108.1 m², of 1.7% of the country's territory. It is 775 meters above sea level. Kastamonu, comprised of mostly rough terrain, has 74.6% mountain and forest area, 21.6% plateaus and 3.8% plain formation. Livestock is denser and brings more snow to Kastamonu, where the land structure is inappropriate, the long and harsh winter, the lack of irrigation facilities, the 59% of its land being forested, and vegetable agriculture is not diverse. Kastamonu, which has 20 counties and 1,073 villages, is the third largest village after Sivas and Sanliurfa. In Kastamonu, milk production and nurturing are the most common of animal farming. The number of ovine in the province of Kastamonu is shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Ovine in Kastamonu City (center and Districts)

Year	Sheep	Goat	Total
2002	81413	26587	108.000
2006	83710	20122	103.832
2007	70653	18217	88.870
2008	66289	17458	83.747
2009	57278	13202	70.480
2010	54569	15692	70.261
2015	70.074	30.369	100.443
2016	69.018	30.372	99.390
2017	63.944	28.872	92.816
2018	65.671	24.744	90.415
2019	69.816	28.247	98.063
2020	82.162	2.691	109.072
2021	83.358	25.630	108.988

Source: TUIK, Retrieved 23.10.2022

² Access Address: URL-2

Ovine breeders use cash credit and credit cards from banks to finance their operations, as do manufacturers in other agricultural areas. Credit cards have a broad user base in the world and in our country, and are especially effective with use opportunities that vary from industry to industry. Although there is not much variation in usage logic, the popularity of the user and the user base is increasing due to the range of various characteristics such as implementation of private campaigns, introduction of different payment terms, and regulation of limit information.

2. Literature Review

A survey of farmers in Tokat province's Central District found that each farmer has a credit card and a majority of one credit card, while the amount of credit card use is influential in age and agricultural product sales, professional experience has shown how many individuals in the family have an education level and the amount of land that doesn't have an impact (Sayılı and Adıgüzel, 2011).

Based on a survey of credit card users in Turkey, there is a significant relationship between socio-economic and demographic characteristics and the use of credit cards (Çavuş, 2006).

According to the survey, which was answered by Vocational School students at Dumlupınar University, the "Impact of Economic Literacy and Credit Card Attitude on Rational Credit Card Use", the height of economic literacy influences the more informed and rational realization of economic decisions (Ünal et.al., 2015).

A survey conducted with employees of the Manisa Forest Service found that credit card use is associated with people's ages, educational conditions and income levels. Furthermore, as a preferred reason for credit card use, it has been determined that there are benefits available through interest rates in order to replace cash usage (Örücü, 2003).

A study in the Erzurum city center aimed at identifying the prevalence of credit card use and factors that affect card use has found that certain major factors influencing credit card ownership are occupations, monthly incomes, cards are beneficial, and the payment method preferred for purchases (Oktay et.al., 2009).

The study of academics' credit card preferences concluded that while it was the bank from which the salary was received for preference reasons and that the bank's image was more influential, the height of the card limits and the influence of being recommended by its relatives was minimal (Çiçek ve Demirdelen, 2010).

A study of credit card users in China found that the prevalence of credit card use declined from the age of 26 to 58 and then began to increase again (Nai et.al., 2018).

The findings of a study in Delhi, India, where credit card use is more intense, show that age, academic competence, marital status, employment status, and income have a significant impact on credit card selection criteria. It is understood from research results that credit card use is higher at 21-40 years of age, that credit card usage is increasing as education is increased; that workers use more cards than non-employees, and that weighted usage is seen by employees in an institution rather than in-house (Banerji and Farooqi, 2017).

3. Method

The survey was used, and surveys were applied to 140 ovine breeders operating in the center and districts of the city of Kastamonu, where results were analyzed. The small number of samples is a significant constraint in research. Due to the difficulties in reaching them, it has been studied with a limited sample.

The first part of a survey conducted asked questions about the demographic characteristics of the survey respondents; the second focus was on the bank's most studied bank and preference reasons; the most common banking product; the problems experienced if any; the use of credit cards; the use of other banking products; and the preferences related to the personnel at the bank, whose use is being studied on how well informed. In addition, recognition of North Anatolian Development Agency (KUZKA) and Agricultural and Rural Development Promotion Agency (TKDK), which were in operation in Kastamonu, was measured.

4. Analyzing Survey Results

Ulusoy and Çelik (2019) also used the scale they made in Kastamonu Provinces and Counties. According to research conducted mainly in the districts of Kastamonu, the vast majority of respondents were working with public banks. It is also stated that interest rates are decisive when applying to the bank. The literacy level of minors is 99.1%, and with their responses to survey questions, people who do not use credit cards are found to be around 1%. One could argue that the business owners have a predominantly 1-3 credit cards. Business owners are often found to be of an individual type of business, and are not capital firms, which tend to give more weight to cash transactions. They complain that banks generally have densities. The widespread availability of the branch network is not considered a lack. This is usually

attributable to the work of public banks and the fact that banks have branches in each county. When studying similar practices, it is well known that our country's rural areas do not pay much attention to post-expenditure checks. When asked if the annual transaction fee was deducted from the credit card, this issue was clearly followed. It is surprising that when a credit card is spent, it is answered that 85% of the slip from the machine is checked. Manufacturers are more interested in farm credit. It is also the result that the manufacturers themselves worked out the bank transactions with the people around them.

The manufacturer does not know where to turn except to the bank when there is a problem with the banks. It is possible to clarify this in the following way in bilateral discussions. When the manufacturer has problems with the bank, it contacts the call-center or the bank's general manager. However, when she is dissatisfied with the overall implementation of the bank, she has a problem with exactly how to communicate it and even where to put it. She is not familiar with such transactions as the Credit Bureau or Findeks Credit Rating.

86.7% of manufacturers already have a loan to pay. A large majority controls the statement of the credit card. In fact, the oral interviews stated that the slip from the pos device compared the card statement, and that it was assisted by family members.

The manufacturer is not interested in capital market instruments. The stock is aware of financial means such as bonds. But she doesn't use it.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

Residence	Central	25.7
	District	74.3
Gender	Female	50.7
	Male	49.3
Age	18-30	7.1
	31-51	30.0
	51 >	62.9
Marital Status	Married	85.7
	Single	0.7
	Other	13.6

Identifying statistics given in Table 2. According to Table 2, most of the participants live in district. While the percentage of men and women is equal, the participants in the interview have been found to be highly aged 50 years or older. Given their marital status, many of the participants are married.

Table3: Answers to survey questions

Base Variable	Sub variable	Percent %
Which bank do you work with the most?	Public	67.9
	Private	32.1
Why do you prefer this bank?	Interest rates	64.3
	Products	5.7
	Familiar advice	8.6
	Interest-free banking	7.1
	Worker interest	14.3
Which is the maximum you are performing?	Credit transactions	39.3
	Cash transactions	60.7
What's your bank handicap?	Credit transactions	21.4
	Branch incompetence	7.1
	Lack of information	17.9
How many credit cards do you have?	Density	53.6
	Not Available	2.1

	1	26.4
	2	25.0
	3	32.1
	4	7.9
	5 and more	6.4
Is the annual operating fee deducted from your credit card?	Yes, I do	25.0
	I don't know	14.3
	No, no	60.7
When you spend it on a credit card, can you check the slip from the machine?	Yes, I do	72.1
	Sometimes	17.1
	No, no	10.7
Which type of loan do you prefer most often?	Consumer	19.3
	Agriculture	57.9
	Other	22.9
How do you get the statement?	Mail	67.9
	Electronics	6.4
	No statement is coming	25.7
Do you handle the banking process for your business?	Yes, I do	62.9
	Sometimes	27.9
	No, no	9.3
Do you know where to apply when you have a problem with the banks?	Yes, I do	77.1
	No, no	22.9
Do you know what the Credit Registration Bureau or Findex is?	Yes, I do	5.7
	No, no	94.3
Do you have a loan to pay?	Yes, I do	92.1
	No, no	7.9
When you learn about your credit card's debt, can you check the monthly statement that came to you?	Yes, I do	92.9
	No, no	7.1
Do you make use of stock market instruments, such as bonds, etc.?	Yes, I do	2.1
	No, no	97.9
Do you read the papers they signed at the bank?	Yes, I do	20.7
	No, no	79.3
Does the gender of the officer at the bank who takes care of you matter?	Yes, I do	5.0
	No, no	95.0
Does the age of the officer at the bank who takes care of you matter?	Yes, I do	8.6
	No, no	91.4
Does it matter that the clerk in the bank who takes care of you is from Kastamonu?	Yes, I do	67.1
	No, no	32.9
Do you do banking online?	Yes, I do	24.3
	No, no	75.7
Do you do banking with a mobile phone?	Yes, I do	11.4
	No, no	88.6
Are you in the bank's private pension fund or have you had private health insurance?	Yes, I do	6.4

	No, no	93.6
Do you know the North Anatolian Development Agency and its activities?	Yes, I do	19.3
	No, no	80.7
Do you know the Agency and activities for Promotion of Agriculture and Rural Development?	Yes, I do	95.7
	No, no	4.3

Manufacturers generally declared that they had signed the bank. When asked if the gender or age of the officer dealing with them at the bank is significant, it is highly irrelevant. But the fact that the countryside is in the province and the demographic nature of the province makes it more likely that the bank officer was born in Kastamonu to make the deal possible. The breeder mostly handles banking from the branch. The uncommon activity of internet banking or mobile banking may be attributed to a lack of concentration in payment instruments, or even specific transactions during the month, with little or no transactions during the other days of the month.

Breeders are aware of private health insurance, but do not control the specifics of the private pension fund. They don't know the activities of the North Anatolian Development Agency. The Rural Development Promotion Agency is well known. If we sort here,, we might say the level of consciousness decreased in the order below.

- Rural Development Promotion Agency
- Chamber of Commerce and Industry
- Commodity Exchange
- North Anatolian Development Agency

Again, one has to remind you that the reputation of the banks or the organizations that operate most is at the forefront of the industry.

5. Result

Financial literacy is an important skill that every individual needs to learn absolutely nowadays. The ability to use earned money (income) and understand variables in the marketplace is a necessity, no matter the situation on the ground. People who do not have financial literacy skills, whether they are an employer or a student or a pensioner, can often have a very difficult time making decisions, even though they usually have adequate economic backlog. They have a hard time concluding their finances, especially when they have multiple choices.

A certain age makes it harder for a particular vocational group. It's almost impossible to make a financial plan or a budget for people who don't have a certain financial knowledge. Understanding the concept of what existence is, how debt is managed, is considered to be fully effective in age, gender, professional groups.

People who have no access to technology, or even have a degree of education, are more likely to have access to information. The ovine sector is one of these sectors. The rural employees who want to get an insight into how the money will be used can most comfortably obtain it from their bank branches. It is possible to learn the alternatives in time, but with regular bank visits, it becomes almost impossible to take advantage of the Internet and tools otherwise.

Because each person can have different expectations, promotional efforts by banks "in line with the expectations of the rural community" can help overcome existing problems. As shown in the analysis of the study, the producers of the Kastamonu Ovine Sector are fully aware of the face-to-face banking processes, but are not aware of other businesses and transactions due to both access to the Internet and the relationship of mobile devices with age. Face-to-face negotiations have also shown them to be reluctant. This is because the concept of "speed" is thought to follow the so-called "reliability" concept, and even the concept of "speed" is not needed. The confidence factor is again taking the citizen to face banking status. The following conclusions are possible with regard to this:

Local businesses in Kastamonu operating in the ovine sectorry, coming together in intra-scale and off-scale conversations;

- They are informative about basic concepts.
- It does not deal with second-generation and third-generation of the sector.
- No financial literacy training was taken.

- Basic banking information is at a high level.
- They feel they don't need Internet or mobile banking information.
- Banking comes from two words: Cash and credit.
- They are regularly working on the revenue-expense account and under the registration.
- When asked what they understand about achieving material success, they describe the point of origin.
- When asked which of the economic variables they are following, two words, "Dollar Index," "Oil price," appear to follow.
- When asked if economic news is being watched, they say that economic news is being watched in major news releases or passed on word of mouth.
- When asked what comes to mind in terms of savings, the answer is "gold."
- They believe that financial literacy is important for the next generation.

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